

BONDED REPAIRS OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH STRUCTURES: PROCESS MONITORING AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

The use of Out-of-Autoclave (OOA) prepregs is attractive for bonded repairs because of their low cure temperature and processability under ambient consolidation pressure. In this study, an 'air breathable' adhesive film was developed and used for co-bonded repairs of nomex sandwich panels with OOA prepregs. Bag and core pressures were measured by means of an instrumented repair fixture to track gas transport throughout the repair cycle. Then, optical microscopy and X-rays analysis were performed to assess repair patch and bondline quality.

The results showed that regardless of the level of moisture in the parent panel, if air channels existed in the adhesive film, much air could be extracted out of the repair cavity and semi-impregnated repair plies. The use of an 'air breathable' adhesive was found beneficial to significantly reduce both repair patch and bondline voidage. In addition, when the adhesive was modified, larger and more regular adhesive fillet could be formed between the honeycomb cell wall and the composite patch.

The use of OOA prepregs with an 'air permeable' adhesive is a promising solution to implement high-quality co-bonded repairs with vacuum bag only pressure.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Sandwich panels are common aerospace high-stiffness structures composed of a core in between two composite face-sheets. While in use, besides moisture exposure, honeycomb sandwich structures experience damage requiring repair. Flush 'soft-patch' scarf bonded repairs of composite face-sheets provide a high property recovery solution; this method involves the co-bonding of repair plies with an adhesive film [1]. A bonded repair is a critical process; it is performed directly on the damaged component by means of a localized heat source under ambient consolidation pressure only.

1.2. Literature Survey

In recent years, semi-impregnated out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepreg systems have been developed, and aim at manufacture primary composite components using vacuum bag only processes [2]. OOA prepregs feature partially impregnated fibre tows that allow entrapped air to be evacuated during a vacuum hold prior to the cure [3]. These high fibre content material systems are attractive for structural bonded repairs as they can be processed at relatively low temperature (93 °C - 121 °C) under ambient pressure only (1 atm) [4]. A previous study showed that a dry media embedded in the adhesive was effective to reduce porosity in bonded repair of monolithic skins with OOA prepregs [5].

Several processing aspects have been studied for the repair of monolithic skins. This includes temperature gradients during cure caused by the localized heat application [6]. Pre-bond moisture influence on repair quality, mechanical strength, fracture toughness, and durability have also been investigated [7-11]. Entrapped air, as well as water and solvent out-gassing [12] prior to adhesive gelation was reported to be the main source of porosity in adhesive bonding of monolithic panels. Bonded repairs of honeycomb sandwich panels present additional challenges because of the significant

volume of air and possible entrapped moisture underneath the face-sheet, which is likely to pressurize upon the application of heat [13, 14]. Vacuum bag only processing of sandwich structure was studied in details [15, 16], core pressure is a key parameter to achieve acceptable skin compaction and core/skin adhesion. If the repair process is inadequate, poor patch consolidation can lead to patch wrinkles, bondline thickness variation, porosity, and debonds [1]. Because most of the load in a shallow angle scarf repair is transferred in shear, voids in the adhesive reduce the repair static [17] and fatigue strength [18].

1.3. Objective

This paper investigates whether air permeable adhesive films are effective means to improve consolidation of repair plies and bondline quality, for both cases of fully and partially wet damaged honeycomb panels cured under ambient pressure conditions. Core and bag pressure are measured to track their evolution during the pre-cure vacuum hold and cure. Finally, optical microscopy and radiographic (X-ray) analysis of specimens were performed to assess repair quality in repair patch and bondline.

2. METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Materials

The material used for the parent skin and repair plies was OOA prepreg Cytec Cycom[®] 5320 featuring an 8-harness fibre bed architecture (T650-35 3K 8HS, 372 g/m² areal weight, 36 % resin content). The repair adhesive film used was the popular 121 °C cure Cytec FM[®] 300-2M (293 g/m² areal weight). For both parent structure and repair core plug, a 19 mm thick over-expanded cell aramid honeycomb core (ECA-R 3/16-4.0) from Euro-Composites[®] Corp. was chosen. An AR 2000 Rheometer by TA Instruments was used to determine the prepreg resin and adhesive film viscosity behaviour and gelation time.

2.2. Engineered Adhesive

As demonstrated in [19, 20], air permeability of OOA prepreps is highly anisotropic, and very low transverse air permeability values were measured for low crimped fibre architecture such as harness satin fabrics used in this work. Because the patch is surrounded by pristine materials in the repair cavity, in-plane air evacuation is not possible and only through thickness air evacuation is available, but difficult. To overcome this lack of air evacuation capability, the adhesive film was re-engineered to allow the gas to pass through the repair area by means of embossing [21] and perforation of the adhesive film as shown in Figure 1. This so-called ‘engineered adhesive’ strategy also features the addition of a thin non-woven glass veil that provides a pathway for air within the core and the semi-impregnated prepreg repair plies. After putting in place the modified or un-modified adhesive film, concentric circles plies of prepreg were laid up to fill the repair scarf cavity, followed by a perforated release film, a nylon breather that connected the glass veil to the vacuum line, and the vacuum bag.

Figure 1: Cross section schematic of the ‘engineered adhesive’ technique over the repair cavity.

2.3. Repair Set-up and Conditioning Method

A quasi-isotropic lay-up [$\pm 45 / 0-90$]_s was used for the parent composite face-sheet and the repair patch matched the parent structure lay-up with the addition of a ± 45 filler ply. The 1.45 mm thick parent composite skin was manufactured with a 51 mm internal diameter cavity and a circular 3 ° repair scarf angle. Surface preparation was achieved by an air powered sander with P120 silicon carbide disks. Contrary to a real-life repair, the cleaned surface was sealed and chemically released to allow all tests to be performed on the same parent structure.

As shown in Figure 2, the experimental fixture of [19] was used to conduct the repairs of this study. The apparatus consists of an aluminium plate with a 150 x 150 mm cavity, on top of which the 280 x 280 mm single-skin sandwich parent panel was placed. Two rows of silicon rubber stripes and hold-down toggle clamps were used to properly seal the parent laminate on top of the aluminium cavity for accurate core pressure measurements. After bagging the repair with conventional consumables, temperatures, internal core and bag pressures were measured by calibrated type-K thermocouples and Wika A-10 pressure transmitters, throughout the 4 hours pre-cure vacuum hold and vacuum cure in a convection oven. The material systems manufacturer's recommended cure cycle was used; it consisted of a heat ramp of 1.7 °C/min to 121 °C followed by a dwell of 4 hours at 121 °C.

Figure 2 : Pictures of the experimental repair set-up; a) aluminium fixture with single-skin sandwich parent panel and clamping system; b) application of the adhesive over the honeycomb repair plug; c) repair set-up in the oven with vacuum and pressure reading gauges plugged in; d) repair patch after cure.

Before the repairs, the parent structure was fully dried at 140 °C for an hour in a convection oven. For the 'partly wet' configurations, the parent structure was immersed in a 65 °C water bath for an hour prior to the repair in a house-built conditioning chamber. Traveller honeycomb coupons were used to measure weight change induced by moisture ingress. After lay-up, the average pre-repair water uptake for the dry configuration was 0.15 ± 0.07 wt. %, while when the parent structure was conditioned, the pristine core had gained 4.18 ± 0.50 wt. %.

A total of six repairs were performed for this paper as displayed in Table 1. Four repairs were performed on a fully dry parent sandwich panel with and without the air breathable adhesive film. Two other repairs were done on a partly wet base sandwich panel. At all time, room conditions were controlled and in the range of 22 ± 2 °C and 25 ± 5 % RH.

#	Adhesive film type	Parent structure condition
1-2	Baseline	Dry
3-4	Engineered adhesive	Dry
5	Baseline	Partly wet
6	Engineered adhesive	Partly wet

Table 1 : Test matrix with adhesive and parent structure conditions.

2.4. Quality Assessment

Three 25 mm long specimens were sectioned from each repair to examine the patch microstructure. Samples were embedded in epoxy resins pucks and polished up to 0.3 µm with a Forcipol variable speed grinder/polisher equipped with a Forcimat automatic head. An up-right optical microscope

Nikon Eclipse L150 with a 100 x 100 mm Märzhäuser motorized stage was used along with Clemex Captiva to capture large images of the patch quality.

The bondline quality was first assessed by optical observation of the released bondline surface with a digital microscope (Dino-lite AM 70130 ZT 5). A finer observation of the adhesive quality was achieved by means of X-rays taken on 30 x 18 mm regions of the bondline at a resolution of 8.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ on a Skyscan 1172 micro-CT. The radiographic parameters included no filter, a voltage source of 40 kV and an intensity of 250 μA .

Void contents were measured by thresholding optical micrographs and radiographs to binary images of porosity with the image processing software ImageJ. Four measures of voidage were performed for each repair specimen.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Pressure Readings during Repair Processing

Oven air, aluminium jig, and top of repair patch temperatures were acquired for each repair. Bag and core pressure were also measured. Recording started when vacuum was introduced in the repair bag, throughout pre-cure vacuum hold, until the end of the cure cycle. The prepreg resin and bonding adhesive rheological characterization indicated that the adhesive gelled 70-75 minutes after beginning of cure, at this moment the prepreg resin viscosity was minimal and gelled about 1 hour later. Material gelation times are indicated on the graphs in Figure 3 along with bag and core pressure measurements.

Figure 3 : Measured repair temperature, bag and core pressure during pre-cure vacuum hold and oven cure of the repair with a baseline adhesive a) and b); and with the engineered adhesive c) and d). Parent structure condition was dry for a) and c); and partly wet for b) and d).

Regardless of the moisture level of the parent structure, if no air-breathable adhesive was used for the repair, the core pressure remained high around ambient air pressure (1000 mbar) until the end of the four hour room temperature vacuum hold (Fig 3 a-b). After the temperature raised into 70-100 °C range, core pressure decreased with a noticeable rise in bag pressure, which was much larger in

presence of moisture in the parent structure (Fig 3 b). It was well documented in [13] that transverse air permeability of OOA prepreg increases at higher temperature. In these trials, as the pressure in the core exceeded the consolidation pressure, pressurized hot gas (air and water, depending on the trial) might have passed through the repair patch or the bondline before adhesive gelation, potentially creating debonds or voids. After the adhesive gelled, core pressure drops are believed to be caused by air in the core passing through the released repair surface to the vacuum bag. Indeed, after gelation, the only path for air is the release repair surface, and similar kinetic in core pressure change during post-cure vacuum bag vents were observed for all tests.

For all trials performed with the engineered adhesive film, as soon as vacuum was applied in the bag, bag and core pressure instantaneously dropped to reach high level of vacuum until the end of the four hour pre-cure vacuum hold (Fig 3 c-d). During the heat ramp, depending on the level of moisture present in the surrounding core, the increase in core pressure is attributed to adhesive flow likely closing air channels in the bondline. Low rise in core pressure, below 100 mbar, was measured for a dry parent structure (Fig 3 c), but up to 400 mbar increase was measured in the presence of pre-repair moisture (Fig 3 d), which was still half of the consolidation pressure (1000 mbar), hence before adhesive gelation, debonds or air passing through the adhesive or the patch is unlikely.

As previously mentioned, because the repair surface was released, after the adhesive gelation core pressure readings are not believed to be meaningful as air can pass through the released scarf surface, which would not happen in real repair. This being said, the experimental fixture was able to provide insightful information on repair pressurization levels until adhesive gelation. Furthermore, previous investigations on monolithic panels suggested no difference in repair microscopic quality whether the repair surface was released or not. Another limitation of the experimental fixture comes from the fact that the parent structure only features one skin, letting all ingress moisture in the core to be released in the fixture cavity. In a realistic scenario, hot moist air from the core is constrained by two composite face sheets and only the core cells' walls directly in the vicinity of the repair cavity would release ingressed moisture. Therefore, for conditioned parent panels, it is believed that the current set-up generates rather conservative experimental conditions.

3.2. Quality Evaluation

After each repair, the repair patch was removed from the released cavity and optically inspected for manufacturing defects with a digital camera. A striking difference in adhesive quality was observed between repairs performed with and without the engineered bondline independently of the parent structure conditioning. As shown in Figure 4, almost no void was found when an air breathable adhesive was used, whereas numerous large and small voids were obvious with a naked eye when an un-modified adhesive film was used for co-bonding. In addition, a much larger bleeding was observed in the breather for repairs performed without the 'engineered adhesive'. In these cases, core pressure was high, pushing resin and adhesive out of the patch fibre bed.

Figure 4 : Representative images of released repair surface of dry parent panels with a) baseline adhesive and b) engineered adhesive. Note that in a), the circled regions with dotted lines indicate large void that were not exposed on the surface.

Then, X-ray images of each specimen were taken to confirm the optical observations of the adhesive quality as shown in Figure 5. Similarly to optical inspections, many large voids, above 1 mm^2 , were measured for all repairs performed with an un-modified adhesive film. In contrast, when an air-breathable adhesive was used, considerably less porosity was noticed. In all cases, the most porous areas in the bondline were in the patch ply drop-off resin rich regions, where the bondline is locally thicker.

Figure 6 displays representative repair patches microstructures and adhesive fillets morphology. Interlaminar voids were found in all analysed patches, but intra-tow micro-porosity was largely reduced for repairs made with a breathable adhesive film. In this case, when vacuum was applied, the compaction pressure ‘squeezed out’ the entrapped air in the repair plies, towards the embossed adhesive that was connected to the vacuum line, leading to a reduction of voidage in the bondline and patch. Moreover, regardless of parent the structure condition, larger regular adhesive fillet were noticed when a modified adhesive was used. This highlight the fact that vacuum was reached in the core at adhesive gelation. Regular large adhesive menisci were found to significantly increase peel [22] and flatwise tension [23] strength of nomex core bonded to composite skins.

Figure 7 summarizes the average bondline and patch voidage found in all repairs. The use of an ‘air breathable’ adhesive film significantly reduced porosity in the patch (from 2.8 % to 1.5 %) and in the adhesive (from 17.0 % to 1.2 %). Whether the parent panel was fully dry or partly wet did not significantly change the adhesive or patch voidage in the performed trials.

Air evacuation is the main driver to achieve low void content in the bondline when using OOA prepreg as repair materials. If entrapped air in the semi-impregnated tows cannot be evacuated, unacceptable levels of porosity are found in the bondline as well as in the patch (intra-tow micro porosity), potentially reducing the strength recovery capability of a co-bonded repair.

Figure 5 : Representative X-ray micrographs showing bondline areal voidage for each of the four repair configurations; a) dry & baseline adhesive; b) partly wet & baseline adhesive; c) dry & ‘engineered adhesive’; d) partly wet & engineered adhesive.

Figure 6 : Representative optical micrographs of adhesive fillets morphology and repair patches microstructure performed over a dry parent sandwich panel; a) using a baseline adhesive; b) using an engineered adhesive.

Figure 7 : Average and standard deviation of measured void content in repair patch cross sections

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study investigated the effect of an ‘air breathable’ adhesive film on co-bonded repairs of Nomex sandwich panels with semi-impregnated prepreg repair plies under vacuum-bag only pressure. Repairs were processed on an instrumented repair fixture to measure bag and core pressure evolution during a pre-cure vacuum hold and the cure. Bondline and repair patch quality were assessed by optical microscopy and X-rays.

The results highlighted the benefits of having an ‘air-breathable’ adhesive film to extract the air out of the repair plies and the honeycomb core. Regardless of parent structure moisture condition, when air could pass through the adhesive film, a considerable reduction in void content in the adhesive was achieved, as well as a decrease in patch micro-porosity. The use of an ‘engineered adhesive’ also led to reach vacuum in the repair cavity, which is responsible for large regular fillet between the honeycomb cell walls and the composite patch. All of these observed improvements in repair quality are likely to enhance the overall strength recovery and durability of bonded repairs performed with semi-impregnated prepregs materials and an ‘air breathable’ adhesive film.

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